

THE PROBLEM OF OBESITY AND TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Abstract. Obesity plays an inevitable role in increasing the prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus, a chronic condition in which the body does not produce enough insulin or cannot utilize insulin efficiently, resulting in elevated blood glucose levels as its primary manifestation. Type 2 diabetes mellitus is characterized by low insulin secretion by β -cells and peripheral insulin resistance, resulting in increased levels of fatty acids. This causes decreased glucose transport to muscle cells, increased fat breakdown and glucose production by the liver. Studies have shown that overweight and obesity account for 80-85% of the risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus in humans. Obesity and diabetes mellitus are chronic diseases that are on the rise worldwide, requiring new approaches to the treatment and prevention of diabetes in obese people. Therefore, it is important to understand the mechanistic link between the two and develop an integrated approach to increase life expectancy and improve quality of life in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and obesity. It has reached pandemic proportions, making the treatment of obesity critical for the prevention and management of type 2 diabetes mellitus worldwide. Numerous clinical studies have shown that moderate and sustained weight loss can improve blood glucose levels, insulin action and reduce the need for diabetic medications. This approach also greatly helps in the prevention, control and remission of diabetes mellitus. Also obesity directly affects cardiovascular disease risk factors including dyslipidemia, type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension and sleep disorders. This literature review aims to provide an up-to-date analysis of epidemiological data on obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus to determine their interrelationships and to estimate the associated prevalence of these diseases.

Keywords: type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity, cardiovascular diseases, childhood obesity.

Introduction. The rapid development of modernization, urbanization and accelerated socio-economic growth has contributed to higher living standards, but on the other hand to stressful and sedentary lifestyles and unhealthy eating habits in most parts of the world. Especially in the last two decades, obesity has become a life-threatening global pandemic, affecting almost every organ system and is now a major public health problem as one of the most prevalent non-communicable diseases. All countries without exception are now affected by obesity, and the impact is projected to become even more pronounced in the current decade, leading to more lost years of healthy life, disability and death [4,5,6,18].

The growing burden of obesity over the past few decades has led to a steady increase in the prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Both obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus are associated with insulin resistance. In obese individuals, adipose tissue, especially in visceral fat depots, releases increased amounts of unesterified fatty acids (UFAs), hormones and anti-inflammatory cytokines that are closely associated with the development of insulin resistance.

The progressive increase in insulin resistance accompanied by impaired pancreatic beta-cell function leads to an inability to control glucose levels in obese patients [8,19,20].

Consequently, this review will examine the associated prevalence of obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus by analyzing current epidemiological data.

Methodology. Interestingly, in 2022, 2.5 billion adults aged 18 years and older were overweight; of these, more than 890 million adults were obese. This means that 43% of adults aged 18 and older (43% of men and 44% of women) were overweight; in comparison, in 1990, only 25% of adults aged 18 and older were overweight [1,2,3,4,5,6,18].

The prevalence of obesity in the United States has increased alarmingly over the past decade. According to published data from 2017 to 2020, 42.4% of adults have a BMI ≥ 30 kg/m², while 20.9% of youth have a BMI ≥ 30 kg/m² [3,4,5,6,7]. In Uzbekistan, the prevalence of obesity in men is 23.1% and in women 34.7%.

According to WHO, in all countries, regardless of income level, women were less physically active than men; 27 per cent of women and 20 per cent of men were classified as not physically active enough.

Obesity plays an inevitable role in the rising prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus, a chronic disease in which the body does not produce enough insulin or cannot utilize insulin effectively, leading to elevated blood glucose levels as its primary manifestation. It is the fastest growing pandemic and public health emergency in the world. According to the latest estimates by the International Diabetes Federation, 537 million people have diabetes mellitus. The number of patients with diabetes mellitus is projected to increase to 643 million by 2030 and 783 million by 2045. It should be noted that more than 90 per cent of all diabetes cases are attributable to type 2 diabetes. In 2021, 541 million adults were diagnosed with impaired glucose tolerance and 319 million adults were diagnosed with impaired fasting glucose levels. These numbers are projected to increase to 730 million and 441 million respectively by 2045. Many studies have shown that the relative risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus is 3.5 times higher in men and 4.6 times higher in women with a BMI greater than 29.9 kg/m² compared with their same sex counterparts with a BMI less than 24.9 kg/m².

In 2021, diabetes was the direct cause of 1.6 million deaths, and of these, 47% were due to diabetes before the age of 70 years. A further 530 000 deaths from kidney disease were caused by diabetes, and high blood glucose levels are responsible for about 11% of deaths from cardiovascular disease [9,13,14,16].

According to the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2023, 357,066 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus were registered in RSS and PMC of Endocrinology named after Acad. Yo. H. Turakulov. Estimates in 2019 showed that 77 million people in India have diabetes and the number is expected to rise to over 134 million by 2045. Approximately 57 per cent of these people remain undiagnosed.

It is worth noting that according to the research, among the regions, the largest number of people with diabetes live in the Western Pacific (163 million), followed by the South East Asia region (88 million), Europe (59 million), the Middle East and North Africa (55 million), and North America and the Caribbean (47.6 million). Currently, the lowest numbers are in South and Central America (36.1 million) and Africa (19.4 million). Thus, it is clear that the wealthy regions of Europe and North America are not the only ones facing a diabetes epidemic.

According to 2019 International Diabetes Federation data, the top three countries with the highest number of people with diabetes are China (116.4 million), India (77.0 million) and the United States of America (31.0 million). This trend is expected to continue in 2030 and 2045, with China (140.5 and 147.2 million) and India (101.0 and 134.2 million) continuing to have the highest

burden of diabetes. This is supported by the Global Burden of Disease study, which reports that population growth and ageing in the world's largest countries, such as China and India, are driving the absolute increase in the number of people with diabetes. [9,10,11].

Results and discussion. Studies have shown that, between 2000 and 2019, by age, the diabetes mortality rate increased by 3%. In lower-middle income countries, the diabetes mortality rate increased by 13%.

In fact, more than 80% of people with type 2 diabetes mellitus are classified as overweight or obese. These two pathologies are deeply interrelated, as they share many common pathophysiological mechanisms [12,16].

And it should be noted that cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are the leading cause of mortality in developed and many developing countries. It has been shown that abdominal obesity plays a key role in the development of CVD risk factors (dyslipidemia, arterial hypertension (AH), carbohydrate metabolism disorders) and is an independent risk factor for the development of type 2 diabetes mellitus and CVD [12,13,16].

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in type 2 DM2. From 1998 to 2015, cardiovascular mortality rates in the United States were observed in 25% of people with diabetes, with cardiovascular mortality remaining higher among people with diabetes in the United States and similar results observed in other Western countries. (14)

In addition, the researchers found an increased burden of elevated BMI, with high BMI causing 4.0 million deaths in 2015, more than two-thirds of which were due to cardiovascular disease (CVD), even accounting for smoking and poor health. Moreover, a significant proportion of both BMI-related deaths 41% and BMI-related disability 34% were due to cardiovascular disease among obese people [15,16,21].

According to WHO, childhood obesity is one of the most serious problems of the 21st century. There are several reasons for this WHO statement. According to the Global Burden of Disease Study, health hazards such as global exposure to unsafe sanitation, household air pollution, underweight children, stunting in children and smoking declined by more than 25 per cent between 1990 and 2015. Over the same period, the risks associated with high body mass index (BMI) increased by more than 25 per cent. The prevalence of obesity has doubled in more than 70 countries since 1980. In 2015, a total of 107.7 million children were obese. Cardiovascular risk markers are clearly associated with cardiovascular disease that can be detected in adults as well as prepubertal children. In children as early as 7-8 years of age, associations between early signs of atherosclerosis and obesity have been observed. Approximately 1 in 4 young people with type 2 diabetes mellitus have microvascular complications or hypertension at the time of diagnosis.

Non-communicable diseases are responsible for about 70% of deaths worldwide. In 2019, diabetes was the ninth leading cause of death, with about 1.8 million cases directly related to hyperglycemia. In addition, cardiovascular disease, which is the leading cause of death and is usually a chronic complication of diabetes, claimed about 9 million lives in the same year. From 2019 to January 2021, the 2019 coronavirus disease pandemic (COVID-19) has already surpassed the global death toll from diabetes with more than 2 million deaths; however, diabetes was again an important risk factor for mortality or development of severe COVID-19 infection.

Even if diabetes does not cause premature death, it causes significant morbidity with disability, reduced productivity and reduced quality of life.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the results of the literature review confirm the significant prevalence of obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus, as well as their close relationship, which is due

to common pathogenetic mechanisms and risk factors. Epidemiological analysis shows an increasing trend in morbidity, which contributes to the growing social and economic burden on health care. According to WHO, diabetic patients are more likely to incur catastrophically high personal health care costs. As a result of a systematic review, it has been shown that the direct annual medical costs of diabetes worldwide are more than \$827 billion. Recognizing the relevance of these diseases is essential for the development and implementation of comprehensive prevention and treatment strategies. This review highlights the need for further in-depth research into these diseases, their risk factors and mechanisms of pathogenesis, which in turn will improve the management of these conditions and the quality of life of patients.

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